

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids. Part II* Gravimetric Determination and Separation of Praseodymium and Neodymium with *N-m-Tolyl-m-Nitrobenzohydroxamic* Acid by Direct Weighing

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A quantitative gravimetric determination of praseodymium and neodymium in the presence of various diverse ions can be made by precipitation with *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid*. The samples containing 6.48 and 6.58 mg of praseodymium and neodymium were precipitated at pH 8.6-9.2 and 8.8-9.5 respectively. The complexes having the composition $(C_{14}H_{11}N_2O_4)_3$ Pr or Nd were weighed directly after drying at 110°. An attempt has been made to separate Pr from Nd.

SOME substituted hydroxamic acids such as *N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid* have been used as useful gravimetric reagents for the determination of many common metals with success^{1,2}. However, for the rare earths like, Ce, La, Pr, Nd, Th, U etc. greater accuracy is essential. The presence of a bulky group in *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid* (*N-m-T-m-NBHA*) and its selectivity as a precipitating reagent for many rare earths^{3,4} in different ranges of pH have made it possible to separate and estimate gravimetrically praseodymium and neodymium respectively from the foreign ions and other rare earths. The accuracy obtained in the present method using this new reagent, *N-m-T-m-NBHA*, for the gravimetric determination of Pr and Nd is a very encouraging factor for the separation and gravimetric determination of Pr or Nd from several commonly occurring metals and rare earths.

An attempt has also been made to separate out Pr from Nd.

Experimental

Chemicals: All the chemicals were used by G. R. and AnalaR grades of E. Merck and B. D. H. respectively.

Reagent: The *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid* (*N-m-T-m-NBHA*) was synthesized by the procedure of Agrawal and Tandon⁵, m.p. 118° (reported m.p. 118°⁶). Its purity was checked by IR, UV and TLC.

The stock solutions of praseodymium and neodymium were prepared by dissolving 1 g each of praseodymium and neodymium nitrate into 500 ml of water and final concentrations were determined volumetrically⁶. Each of 10 ml solutions contain 6.48 mg and 6.58 mg of Pr and Nd respectively.

A 1% of masking agents (cyanide, oxalate, citrate and magnesium EDTA) were prepared by dissolving the requisite amount in double distilled water.

Procedure: In a litre beaker, 10 ml solution of praseodymium (6.48 mg) or neodymium (6.58 mg) and about 500 ml of distilled water were heated at 60° on water bath. Then about 20 ml of 0.01M solution of *N-m-T-m-NBHA* in ethanol was added dropwise with constant stirring followed by 0.1M solution of ammonium hydroxide until complete precipitation was obtained. The pH of precipitation is 8.6-9.2 and 8.8-9.5 for Pr and Nd respectively and was adjusted by ammonium chloride. The granular complexes thus obtained were digested for 30 min on a water bath, filtered through sintered glass crucible of porosity G4, washed thoroughly with hot water and finally with 20% aqueous ethanol (10 × 10 ml). The complexes were dried at 110° and weighed directly as $(C_{14}H_{11}N_2O_4)_3$ Pr or Nd.

Separation and gravimetric determination of praseodymium(III) from common metals

Masking: 10 ml portion of Pr (III) (0.001M) was mixed with known amounts of the foreign metal ions and diluted to 500 ml. The pH value was adjusted between 8.6-9.2 with ammonium hydroxide (0.01M) and nitric acid (0.01M). A 10 ml portion of 1% solution of potassium cyanide was added and the mixture was heated upto 60°. The reagent solution was added dropwise with constant stirring. The complex thus formed was allowed to stand for about 30 min. on the water bath. It was filtered, dried and weighed as before.

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Pr (III) could be separated from and determined in presence of Ag^+ , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and Ga^{3+} . Similarly Pr (III) was precipitated with *N-m-T-m-NBHA* and separated from Pb^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Be^{2+} , Sb^{3+} , Sn^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , Zn^{4+} and Ti^{4+} by using 10 ml of 1% citrate and oxalate solution as masking agents in place of cyanide. Pr (III) was separated from Al^{3+} , V^{5+} and Mo^{6+} by using Mg-EDTA as a masking agent.

Adjusting pH: A 10 ml solution of praseodymium (0.001 *M*) was mixed with desired foreign ions and the Ag^+ , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , Cd^{2+} and Mg^{2+} were precipitated below the pH 6.5 with *N-m-T-m-NBHA* using in excess. The precipitate was filtered, washed, dried and from mother liquor Pr was precipitated at pH 8.6-9.2.

Separation from rare earths and transuranic metals

Praseodymium (III) was separated from Th^{4+} , U^{6+} and Ce^{4+} by precipitating these ions at pH 3.8-4.8 with *N-m-T-m-NBHA* and later Pr (III) was precipitated from mother liquor at pH 8.6-9.2.

Praseodymium (III) was determined in presence of La^{3+} by precipitating Lanthanum at pH 7.5-8.5 and then Pr was reprecipitated from the mother liquor.

Sm^{3+} and Gd^{3+} were not interfering with the precipitation of Pr^{3+} as they are precipitated at pH 9.6 with the same reagent.

Separation and gravimetric determination of neodymium (III) from common metals

Masking: A 10 ml of Nd^{3+} (0.001 *M*) was mixed with the desired foreign metal ions and diluted to 500 ml. The pH was adjusted to 8.8-9.5 with ammonium hydroxide (0.01 *M*) and nitric acid (0.01 *M*). A 10 ml portion of 1% solution of KCN was added and the contents were heated upto 60°. The reagent solution was added dropwise with constant stirring. The complex formed was allowed to stand for about 30 min. It was filtered, dried and weighed as described before. $\text{Nd}(\text{III})$ was separated from and determined in presence of Ag^+ , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and Ga^{3+} .

$\text{Nd}(\text{III})$ was precipitated by masking from Pb^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Be^{2+} , Sb^{3+} , Sn^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , Zn^{4+} and Ti^{4+} with 1% citrate and oxalate solutions in place of cyanide solution.

$\text{Nd}(\text{III})$ could also be separated from Al^{3+} , V^{5+} and Mo^{6+} by using Mg-EDTA for masking.

Adjusting pH: A 10 ml portion of $\text{Nd}(\text{III})$ was mixed with desired foreign metal ions such as Ag^+ , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Ed^{2+} and Mg^{2+} and diluted to 500 ml. Excess of the reagent solution was added and the pH was adjusted with ammonium hydroxide. The above mentioned ions were

precipitated upto pH 6.5. The precipitates obtained were filtered and washed. $\text{Nd}(\text{III})$ was reprecipitated from the mother liquor by adjusting the pH at 8.8-9.5.

Separation from rare earths and transuranic metals

Nd^{3+} was separated from cerium (IV), thorium (IV) and uranium (VI) by precipitating them at pH between 3.8 to 4.8 and then Nd was precipitated from the mother liquor at the pH 8.8-9.6.

Nd was separated and determined from La^{3+} by precipitating $\text{La}(\text{III})$ at the pH 7.5-8.5 and then precipitating Nd from the mother liquor.

Sm^{3+} and Gd^{3+} did not interfere because the pH of precipitation for these ions is higher than that of Nd^{3+} .

Separation of Pr from Nd

An attempt has been made to separate Pr from Nd by taking advantage of the solubility of these complexes in ethanol as Pr is more soluble than Nd in ethanol.

A solution containing each of 6.48 and 6.58 mg of Pr and Nd was taken in a litre beaker. It was diluted to 500 ml and pH was adjusted to 8.6. The Pr was precipitated with *N-m-T-m-NBHA*. It was filtered, washed and dried. The Nd is not giving any precipitate at this pH. Further the pH was raised to 9.5 to precipitate Nd along with traces of Pr. The Nd complexes were dissolved in alcohol and fractionally crystallized. The first crop was Pr. The second crop was decomposed with perchloric and nitric acid and the solution was diluted to 500 ml. A trace of Pr was precipitated by suitably adjusting the pH 8.6 with *N-m-T-m-NBHA* and Nd was reprecipitated as before. The results on separation of Pr and Nd are shown in Table 5

Results and Discussion

The experimental results on the quantitative determination of praseodymium and neodymium are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The results on the separation of Pr and Nd from several diverse ions are given in Tables 3 and 4 respectively.

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF PRASEODYMIUM WITH *N-m-TOLYL-m-NITROBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID*.

Weight of Praseodymium Taken (mg)	Weight of the complex (mg)	Weight of Praseodymium found (mg)	Error
6.48	43.88	6.48	—
9.72	65.75	9.71	+0.01
9.72	65.89	9.73	-0.01
12.96	87.76	12.96	—
16.20	109.60	16.19	+0.01
32.40	219.40	32.40	—

TABLE 2—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF NEODYMIUM WITH N-*m*-TOLYL-*m* NITROBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID.

Weight of Neodymium taken (mg)	Weight of the complex (mg)	Weight of Neodymium found (mg)	Error
6.58	45.54	6.56	+ 0.02
6.58	43.67	6.58	—
13.16	87.34	13.16	—
19.74	131.00	19.73	+ 0.01
32.90	218.35	32.90	—
32.90	218.35	32.90	—

TABLE 3—SEPARATION AND GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF PRASEODYMIUM FROM OTHER METAL WITH N-*m*-TOLYL-*m*-NITROBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID.

Praseodymium taken (mg)	Diverse Ions (mg)	Masking Agent	Praseodymium found (mg)
9.72	Af ⁺ (SO)	Cyanide	9.74
16.20	Mn ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	16.21
9.72	Zn ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	9.73
9.72	Cd ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	9.71
16.20	Hg ²⁺ (100)	Cyanide	16.19
9.72	Cu ²⁺ (100)	Cyanide	9.72
16.20	Mg ²⁺ (100)	Cyanide	16.20
9.72	Fe ³⁺ (75)	Cyanide	9.72
6.48	Ga ³⁺ (80)	Cyanide	6.48
6.48	Pb ²⁺ (80)	Citrate + Oxalate	6.49
6.48	Pd ²⁺ (80)	Citrate + Oxalate	6.49
9.72	Be ²⁺ (80)	Citrate + Oxalate	9.71
9.72	Sb ³⁺ (80)	Citrate + Oxalate	9.71
9.72	Sn ²⁺ (80)	Citrate + Oxalate	9.71
16.20	Bi ³⁺ (100)	Citrate + Oxalate	16.20
9.72	Zn ²⁺ (100)	Citrate + Oxalate	9.20
16.20	Ti ⁴⁺ (100)	Citrate + Oxalate	16.19
6.48	Al ³⁺ (80)	Mg - EDTA	6.48
6.48	V ⁵⁺ (80)	Mg - EDTA	6.48
9.72	Mo ⁶⁺ (100)	Mg - EDTA	9.72
6.48	U ⁶⁺ (80)	a	6.48
6.48	Th ⁴⁺ (80)	a	6.48
6.48	La ³⁺ (80)	a	6.47
6.48	Ce ³⁺ (80)	a	6.48
6.48	Sm ³⁺ (80)	a	6.49

a = By adjusting the pH

Praseodymium-N-*m*-T-*m*-NBHA Complex : It is a light green complex, readily soluble in ethanol; fairly soluble in dioxane, chloroform, and benzene and only sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride, diethyl ether and acetone. It is decomposed when treated with concentrated sulphuric, nitric, hydrochloric and perchloric acids. The analytical results indicate the composition of complex as (C₁₄H₁₁N₂O₄)₃ Pr and the calculated C, 52.84; H, 3.48; N, 8.80; Pr, 14.77% and found C, 52.83; H, 3.46; N, 8.82; Pr, 14.77%.

Effect of pH : Experimental studies on the determination of Pr in solution of different pH values with all the other factors identical revealed that the precipitation commenced at pH 8.6 and was quantitative in the range 8.6-9.2.

TABLE 4—SEPARATION AND GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF NEODYMIUM FROM OTHER METALS WITH N-*m*-TOLYL-*m*-NITROBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID.

Neodymium taken (mg)	Diverse Ions (mg)	Masking Agent	Neodymium found (mg)
6.58	Ag ⁺ (50)	Cyanide	6.59
13.16	Mn ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	13.17
9.97	Zn ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	9.95
9.97	Cd ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	9.96
9.97	Hg ²⁺ (100)	Cyanide	9.96
9.97	Cu ²⁺ (100)	Cyanide	9.96
13.16	Mg ²⁺ (100)	Cyanide	13.16
9.97	Fe ³⁺ (75)	Cyanide	9.97
6.58	Ca ²⁺ (80)	Cyanide	6.58
6.58	Pb ²⁺ (80)	Citrate + Oxalate	6.58
6.58	Be ²⁺ (80)	Citrate + Oxalate	6.59
6.58	Pd ²⁺ (80)	Citrate + Oxalate	6.59
9.97	Sb ³⁺ (80)	Citrate + Oxalate	9.96
9.97	Sn ²⁺ (80)	Citrate + Oxalate	9.95
13.16	Bi ³⁺ (100)	Citrate + Oxalate	13.17
13.16	Zr ⁴⁺ (100)	Citrate + Oxalate	13.17
13.16	Ti ⁴⁺ (100)	Citrate + Oxalate	13.15
9.97	Al ³⁺ (80)	Mg - EDTA	9.97
13.16	V ⁵⁺ (80)	Mg - EDTA	13.16
13.16	Mo ⁶⁺ (100)	Mg - EDTA	13.15
6.58	U ⁶⁺ (80)	a	6.58
6.58	Th ⁴⁺ (80)	a	6.58
9.97	La ³⁺ (80)	a	9.96
6.58	Ce ³⁺ (80)	a	6.59
6.58	Sm ³⁺ (80)	a	6.59

a = by adjusting the pH

TABLE 5—SEPARATION OF PR FROM ND

Metal taken (mg)		Found, (mg)	
Nd	Pr	Nd	Pr
6.48	6.58	6.39	6.78
6.48	6.58	6.40	6.75
6.48	13.16	6.38	13.22
12.96	19.74	12.93	19.80
16.20	19.74	16.74	19.80

Neodymium-N-*m*-T-*m*-NBHA complex : It is light grey complex, freely soluble in dioxane, chloroform and fairly soluble in alcohol, benzene and sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride, diethyl ether and glacial acetic acid. It is decomposed when treated with concentrated sulphuric, nitric, hydrochloric and perchloric acids. The analytical results indicate the composition of the complex as (C₁₇N₁₁N₂O₄)₃ Nd and the calculated

C, 52.66; H, 3.47; N, 8.77; Nd, 15.06% and found C, 52.65; H, 3.45; N, 1.78; Nd, 15.07%.

Effect of pH : Experimental studies on the determination of Nd in solutions of different pH values with all the factors identical revealed that the precipitation commenced at pH 8.8 and was quantitative in the range 8.8 to 9.5.

Masking agents : The presence of excess of cyanide and magnesium-EDTA did not interfere with the precipitation of Pr and Nd with N-*m*-T-*m*-NBHA while the excess of citrate and oxalate inhibited the precipitation.

Infra red spectra : The infra-red spectra of N-m-T-m-NBHA as a mull showed peaks at 3279, 1600 and 917 cm^{-1} , due to stretching vibration of O-H, C=O and N-O respectively. After complex formation the spectrum does not show any peak regarding the O-H frequency disappears in Pr, Nd-N-m-T-m-NBHA complex, because in the formation of the complex, the hydrogen ion is lost and the oxygen atom of carbonyl group is coordinated with the Pr or Nd.

The absorption peak due to carbonyl (C=O), stretching vibration in the spectra of Pr or Nd-N-m-T-m-NBHA complex is located at 1553 and 1550 respectively due to bonding of carbonyl oxygen atom to the metal -C=O \rightarrow Pr or Nd. The peak due to N-O stretching vibration is almost unaffected in the Pr or Nd-N-m-T-m-NBHA complex.

Precision and accuracy : The present method for the determination of Pr or Nd has the relative error 0.5% with the standard deviation ± 0.005 .

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References

1. K. BHATT and Y. K. AGRAWAL, *Synth. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1972, **2**, 175.
2. S. C. SHOROE, *Analyst.*, 1950, **75**, 27.
3. H. L. KAPOOR, Y. K. AGRAWAL and P. C. VERMA, *Talanta*, 1975, **22**, 193.
4. H. L. KAPOOR and Y. K. AGRAWAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, (in press).
5. Y. K. AGRAWAL and S. G. TANDON, *J. Chem. Engg.*, 1971, **16**, 371.
6. F. J. WECHOR, *Analytical Uses of Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid*, Von Nostrand, New York, 1961.